

PEDAGOGICAL CONTENT OF DEONTOLOGICAL COMPETENCE IN FUTURE TEACHERS

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Abstract: This article is devoted to the deontological preparation of future teachers for professional activities. The article considers issues of working with children, health-saving school conditions and deviant behavior in patriotic education. The deontological preparation of aspects and directions of the university's activity on the formation of the main future teachers will be discussed.

Key words: deontology, readiness, professional training, professional duty, self-awareness, consciousness, compliance with ethical principles, spiritual and intellectual development of students, rather than personal goals. spiritual and intellectual development,

The main part: "deontology" (Greek deon,ontos - necessary; logos - word) is an explanation of morality, the science of ethics. The term "deontology" was first introduced by Bentham, who applied to the theory of ethics. Jeremy (Jeremiah) Bentham - (1748-1832) English philosopher, jurist, one of the founders of the University of London. Organizer and economist, in the field of science, he is famous for developing one of the narrow directions of the theory of utilitarianism (utilitas - useful) puts forward the theory that action should be evaluated in terms of the benefits it brings to people. According to his theory, at the age of 21, I. Bentham left a will that after his death, his body should be transferred to anatomical experiments. I. Bentham called his concept "deontology". In the USSR, this direction has been known since the revolution of 1917, rejecting the entire "heritage of the royal system", under the threat of punishment, the government prohibited the existence of ethics, which is the most important component of any science, including medicine. "Throwing well-known medical ethics into the trash can: only criticism and self-criticism are the basis of the work of a Soviet doctor," he said. At that time, there

were many people with similar views in different fields of science. But medicine cannot be imagined without ethics. In 1946, the founder of Soviet oncology, Nikolai Nikolayevich Petrov, wrote a book on surgical ethics. 70-year-old N.N. Petrov realizes that it is impossible to publish a book on ethics in the USSR and replaces the term "ethics" in the manuscript with the unknown term "deontology". N.N. Petrov's contemporaries and students wrote in their memoirs: "Nikolai Nikolaevich clearly understands that if his replacement is found, he will not return from the camps, but he took a risk. Censor N.N. It turned out to be less knowledgeable than Petrov, and the book burned out ". Nowadays, a term has appeared that is used not only in medicine, but also in other sciences that consider various aspects of the activity of the "person-person" system.

Deontological competence is based on pedagogical content, teachers' adherence to laws and ethical principles. This content takes place in mastering the advice and decisions of teachers, in treating students fairly and conscientiously, in paying attention to the spiritual and intellectual development of students rather than personal goals.

The following important points for teachers are included in the pedagogical content of deontological competence:

1. Adherence to ethical principles: Teachers must commit themselves to complying with laws and ethical principles. They should pay attention to fair treatment of students, protection of their rights and effective teaching.
2. Spiritual and intellectual development of students: Teachers strive to provide academic, spiritual and social opportunities to actively support students, develop and expand themselves.
3. Spiritual and intellectual development of students rather than personal goals: Teachers should consider themselves competent for the spiritual and intellectual development of students. They should avoid harming students rather than personal goals.

Conclusion: In the pedagogical content of deontological competence, these points are essential for teachers and help them to be successful in advising students, developing them and protecting their rights.

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